

Service Design Guide

Susanne Arndt

Version 3, June 2026

Inhalt

1 Introduction	2
1.1 Purpose and Target Group of This Document	2
1.2 Service Design and the Base4NFDI Phases	2
1.3 Service Design Goals – An Overview	3
2 Service Design – Approach and Outcomes	4
2.1 Approach to Service Design	4
2.2 Service Design Documentation	5
2.3 Service Design Aspects	5
3 Overarching Landscape and Goals	6
3.1 NFDI & Base4NFDI – Integration and Re-use	6
3.2 A Look Ahead – Basic Services and EOSC	7
3.3 FAIR Basic Services	9
3.3.1 FAIR-enabling Services	9
3.3.2 FAIR Software and Software Metadata and Quality	9
4 Service Design Aspects to Consider	11
4.1 Procedural Aspects of Service Design	11
4.2 User-related Aspects of Service Design	12
4.2.1 Accessibility	12
4.2.2 User Experience and Ergonomics	12
4.2.3 Service Documentation	14
4.2.4 User Training	14
4.3 Technological Aspects of Service Design	15
4.3.1 Architecture – Components, Modules and Their Dependencies	15
4.3.2 Interfaces, Data Formats and Communication Protocols	16
4.3.3 Service Performance, Health and Delivery	17
4.3.4 Testing	18
4.3.5 Service Security	18
4.4 Communication-related Aspects of Service Design	20
4.4.1 Service Website and Communication Channels	20
4.4.2 Change Management and Communication	20
4.5 Governance- and Compliance-related Aspects of Service Design	21
4.5.1 Assigning Tasks and Responsibilities	21
4.5.2 Compliance	21
5 Conclusion: Don't Panic!	22
Image Credits	24

Funded by DFG as part of NFDI.

Grant Numbers: 521453681, 521460392, 521462155, 521463400, 521466146, 521471126, 521473512, 521474032, 521475185, 521476232

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Target Group of This Document

This document guides you while drafting your **service design** in the Initialisation Phase of Base4NFDI. It lists foundational aspects to consider and directs you to external best practice documents, assisting you in designing a **sustainable basic service**. It also points out the broader context of basic service development. You should gain awareness of it during the Initialisation Phase to **prepare and plan for future integration tasks**.

REMEMBER: YOU DO NOT NEED TO IMPLEMENT ALL ASPECTS INTRODUCED BY THIS GUIDE DURING THE INITIALISATION PHASE YET!

This guide introduces critical dimensions of service design to raise your awareness for them. You should familiarise yourself with these in the Initialisation Phase to avoid blind spots throughout the whole course of the basic service development (incl. Integration and Ramp-up).

1.2 Service Design and the Base4NFDI Phases

Service design is located in the Base4NFDI Initialisation Phase and you must address it early on in your basic service development. It has a particular purpose within the Initialisation Phase but also has importance for the other two Base4NFDI phases.

REMEMBER: During the **Initialisation Phase**, a **prototype** is developed. In the **Integration Phase**, the basic service must meet stricter requirements, **enabling its use** by other consortia's domain-specific applications and adoption by other Base4NFDI services. At the end of the **Ramp-up Phase**, these services must be ready for reliable integration into the wider infrastructure within and potentially beyond the NFDI and must be ready for **reliable operation**.

In the service design process, you establish the foundational structure of your basic service. Based on it, you create your prototype¹ and you update it when the prototype is tested and new requirements emerge. It contains aspects that you must address and fine-tune (e.g. service security) when NFDI consortia integrate it into their services – in particular, when your service is ramping-up for long-term operation. Service design is important groundwork that you should not neglect.

¹ Find some more information about prototyping at Paulius Tvaranavičius et al. (2025) Creating Prototypes, Co-Creation Toolkit for Environmental Services. British Geological Survey (BGS), Natural Environment Research Council (NERC). Available at: <https://nerc-eds.github.io/co-creation-toolkit/toolkit/prototyping/> (last accessed: June 24, 2026).

The [Base4NFDI TA1 Team](#) can support you with the service design and/or its documentation by guiding you through the process and by monitoring the service landscape to ensure that there are no blind spots. The Base4NFDI [Service Stewards](#) can assist you, identifying current technology trends within the consortia and their user bases.

1.3 Service Design Goals – An Overview

The service design process helps you to achieve the following goals for your basic service.

Goal 1: You have identified all required components.

Determine which elements you need to deliver the service – be it staff roles or technical and digital components. Make sure all components serve a purpose in relation to your stakeholders’ requirements.

[4.3.1 Architecture – Components, Modules and Their Dependencies](#)

Goal 2: You are aware of all component interactions and necessary interfaces.

Identify and document which interactions between the components are necessary to support user actions and define interfaces that enable a smooth flow of these interactions. Define how users can communicate with you or how you can communicate with your users.

[4.1 Procedural Aspects of Service Design](#) · [4.3.2 Interfaces, Data Formats and Communication Protocols](#) · [4.4 Communication-related Aspects of Service Design](#) · [4.5.1 Assigning Tasks and Responsibilities](#)

Goal 3: You have defined first quality attributes of your service.

Specify first measurable indicators for service success as a minimum acceptable standard. Use these as your goals, to validate the developed prototype and to verify that service development is going into the right direction.

[2.1 Approach to Service Design](#) · [4.3.3 Service Performance, Health and Delivery](#)

Goal 4: You have located your service convincingly in the broader research infrastructure landscape.

Identify areas of synergy, competition, and unique value proposition in comparison to existing research infrastructures. In particular, identify complementary services that benefit from integrating your service. Identify first interoperability goals you need to achieve.

[3 Overarching Landscape and Goals](#)

visualisation is continued on next page

Goal 5: You know how to optimise your service, e.g. for usability and how to make it compliant with legal requirements and best practices.

Include the user perspective into your design: Make the service simple and easy to use avoiding complex interfaces and user interactions. Think about training your users. Consider legal compliance standards early on, e.g. for accessibility, data protection, security, in order to create a trustworthy service. [4.2 User-related Aspects of Service Design](#) · [4.2.1 Accessibility](#) · [4.3.4 Testing](#) · [4.3.5 Service Security](#) · [4.5.2 Compliance](#)

Goal 6: You have documented your service design.

Capture the service design in a comprehensive documentation. It shall guide your team during the service development as a common reference. Update the documentation when new requirements or user feedback from piloting and testing make changes in the service design necessary. [2.2 Service Design Documentation](#)

2 Service Design – Approach and Outcomes

2.1 Approach to Service Design

Your service design is the **conceptual blueprint** for the entire service, considering all relevant technical, organisational, resource and user aspects. Provide as much detail as needed to enable the construction of the service. The documentation of the design is needed to verify the design against the requirements and quality attributes. Service design, therefore, needs to start with addressing the expected and empirically collected **functional requirements** from the requirements analysis (your Deliverable D.Ini.1)². Based on these functional needs as well as on the software and service evaluation (D.Ini.2), you should try to **identify** appropriate **service components** that can provide or enable the required functionality.

In addition, try to define initial **non-functional requirements** (= quality attributes) for the service (e.g. speed/ efficiency of the system, performance, stability, maintainability, etc.) before finalising your service design and before planning the prototype. Quantify, and if necessary, contact stakeholders to specify them. Also define quality attributes for non-technical services, e.g. acceptable time until external requests are answered.

Choose the **technology stack** according to both types of requirements. Prefer established open source software. Try to document your concept visually using appropriate types of diagrams. Try to aim for a **minimum viable product** (MVP) to speed up development and to have a shareable prototype ready fast. Dissect the service into **functional** (= vertical) and **technical** (= horizontal) **layers** in order to see how user features depend on specific

² The deliverables are required to complete the Initialisation Phase; cf. Wittenhorst, T. et al. (2025) 'Base4NFDI – Requirements for Completion of Initialisation Phase'. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19662240>.

technical components (e.g. API, middleware, data storage, UI), understand how the technical **building blocks** interact and break the service down into smaller parts that can be built and tested separately.

This approach helps you to **prioritise** development and implementation **tasks** (also for non-technical services!), to plan for **iterations**, and to reach the MVP sooner. If required, **refine** the service design by applying (further) quality attributes. **Watch the scope** of the design: Do not let it grow too big, insist on limits to non-functional requirements (in consultation with stakeholders), postpone any optimisation to a later stage of development, and **aim for a prototype** as soon as the draft of your service design seems sufficiently developed.

Before moving on to the prototyping/ development of the service, check again for the consistency of interfaces between components, note boundaries of your system and assign responsibilities within your team. Plan for further iterations of redesign, design changes and more prototypes based on the later piloting and testing of the prototype. If you want to make sure the design is sound, have it reviewed by critical stakeholders. **Remember:** The Initialisation Phase is about **testing the basic concept** and providing the service as a **first prototype**, not delivering the full service!

2.2 Service Design Documentation

The service concept must be documented in your reporting deliverable D.Ini.3 that should be completed as a first draft six months after the start of the Initialisation Phase. Think of this documentation as your roadmap for service development and as a planning instrument: Start with a high-level overview to be refined and updated in further iterations³. The design grows and evolves with iterations, revealing more details. Consider your proposal as a starting point for the documentation of your service design: Relevant sections can feed into your deliverable D.Ini.3. Make sure to track service design tasks in the D.Ini.3 reporting task in OpenProject provided by TA1. Choose accompanying documentation formats that are appropriate for the kind of information you would like to model and that you can handle in the limited time of the Initialisation Phase. Consider which target groups need to understand the documentation of the design. Link any supplements and external documentation to the OpenProject reporting deliverable. Documenting the rationale behind design decisions may also help to prevent repeated discussions later.

2.3 Service Design Aspects

The service design itself must consider a broad range of aspects already. The main **dimensions** of the service design are:

- architectural and technological service aspects (tools, frameworks and methods),

³ Iterations may be required e.g., when new requirements emerge or known requirements need to be refined based on piloting and testing of the prototype.

- the connection/ interaction of the service with other basic services and services within and beyond the NFDI consortia (on a technical and organisational level),
- processes and interactions between users, service and any service providers (e.g. user experience (UX), training, support structures, customer communications),
- service delivery resulting in a specific user experience (human-centeredness),
- resources reliable service delivery (e.g. hardware, human resources),
- legal requirements (e.g. the General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR).

Which dimensions matter most also depends on the type of service you are developing. It is your task to set the right focus while this guide helps you to address all critical points.

Your service is not primarily based on a technical component?

The service design and its documentation should still try to capture its individual components, their dependencies, the context in which it is located, as well as initial quality attributes.

3 Overarching Landscape and Goals

The development of basic services in Base4NFDI shall result in mature basic services that

- adhere to a common framework and shared quality standards,
- are relevant to a majority of NFDI consortia, and
- bring added value to the domain-specific services of the consortia.

Ultimately, basic services need to contribute to the facilitation of Open Science and FAIR⁴ Research Data Management (FAIR = Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).

3.1 NFDI & Base4NFDI – Integration and Re-use

The integration of your basic service into the NFDI landscape is a dedicated concern of the Base4NFDI Integration Phase⁵. However, think about the types of users or services that would benefit from your service already in the Integration Phase to plan the search for integration candidates and interested parties. You probably already gathered some of their requirements so that you can address these in the service design as well.

The design of your basic service should also include some considerations about the re-use of the other basic services developed in the Base4NFDI project. These provide support in any tasks that your service may need, but are not at its core. For example,

- user authentication and authorisation are addressed by IAM4NFDI,
- terminologies are addressed by TS4NFDI,

⁴ cf. Wilkinson, M.D. et al. (2016) 'The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship', *Scientific Data*, 3(1), p. 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>. URL: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/> (last accessed: June 23, 2026).

⁵ cf. [Schäfer-Neth et al. 2025](#)

- persistent identifiers (PIDs) are addressed by PID4NFDI.

You can find a complete overview of all basic services on the Base4NFDI website⁶. Base4NFDI supports your project via dedicated events where you can learn more about the other basic services and can connect to the other teams.

Integrations within the NFDI and Base4NFDI are mostly realised as service-to-service connections. **Remember:** You do not need to integrate these services during the Initialisation Phase! You should rather identify dependencies resulting from planned integration shaping your service and its components⁷.

The NFDI infrastructure is the immediate context of the basic service development. However, ongoing initiatives on the international level become relevant as well: the NFDI engages in becoming a national node within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)^{8,9,10,11} which brings further requirements to services developed in this context.

3.2 A Look Ahead – Basic Services and EOSC

EOSC is a very dynamic environment. The EOSC EU Node (EEN) launched in October 2024 and the NFDI has recently accelerated its efforts to develop the national EOSC node for Germany¹². Conceptual documents are provided and updated continuously. The EOSC Federation Handbook may help you to get a first overview of what EOSC is, what its requirements are and how one can join. It describes the European Open Science Cloud as a “system of systems” and the federated architecture of the different nodes to be integrated into this system. It explains basic node capabilities required for the envisaged federation. Furthermore, it describes how services can join the EOSC federation from a legal and technical view. In the future, it will also define a set of policies that need to be followed by candidate nodes.

⁶ <https://base4nfdi.de/projects> (last accessed: June 23, 2026)

⁷ NFDI working groups produce outcomes for infrastructure-related topics you should take note of, e.g. *WG Overall Architecture* in NFDI Section *Common Infrastructure* or *TF Governance and Sustainability*. The latter has recently published cornerstones for the operation of an NFDI service portfolio. [Busse et al. 2025](#) define criteria for portfolio admission, [Deschler et al. 2025](#) categorize financial needs of services which require funding.

- [\[Busse et al. 2025\]](#) Busse, C. et al. (2025) ‘Leistungsfähige Entscheidungsstrukturen für ein NFDI-Dienstportfolio – Impulse zu Kriterien, Entscheidungsverfahren und Portfoliomanagement’. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.16356842>.
- [\[Deschler et al. 2025\]](#) Deschler, K. et al. (2025) ‘Finanzflüsse für Dienste und Aufgaben – Impulse zur Kategorisierung von Finanzbedarfen nach Leistungsarten’. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.16357819>.

⁸ Cf. for example the EOSC EU Node: <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/> (last accessed: June 23, 2026)

⁹ Cf. <https://www.nfdi.de/nfdi-is-part-of-eoscs-build-up-phase/?lang=en> (last accessed: June 23, 2026)

¹⁰ For the integration of NFDI services into the EOSC EU Node see Lechowska-Winiarz, K., Wilk, R., & Gutiérrez, M. (2025). EOSC Beyond D15.1 Service integration plans of the EOSC Pilot Nodes. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17569393>.

¹¹ Wetzels, T. (2025) ‘The NFDI Pilot node & the EB Sandbox’. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15703050>. Presentation held at the EOSC Beyond Webinar *Exploring the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox* on June 19, 2025. Recording of the presentation: <https://youtu.be/98opDJi91CU?t=1863> (last accessed: June 23, 2026).

¹² Find more information about the national node for Germany at <https://eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation/eosc-node-germany> (last accessed: June 23, 2026)

[EOSC Association 2026] EOSC Association (2026) ‘EOSC Federation Handbook’. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18454649>.

- Homepage: <https://eosc.eu/eosc-federation-handbook/> (last accessed: June 23, 2026).

Base4NFDI observes the EOSC development closely and tries to position itself to it, for example with the white paper by [Bernard et al. 2024](#), which tries to define interoperability goals for the Base4NFDI phases¹³.

[Bernard et al. 2024] Bernard, L. et al. (2024) ‘Base4NFDI Policy Paper: “Base4NFDI Services and EOSC: Guidance for Interoperability”, Version 1’. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.13946300>.

While you do not have to meet any requirements for EOSC compatibility and interoperability in the Initialisation Phase, yet, you should at least become aware of them. The aim with regard to EOSC during the Initialisation Phase is to raise awareness and be prepared. The whitepaper suggests the following timeline for EOSC interoperability:

The TA1 team can support you with any questions. The Base4NFDI team will furthermore discuss possible integration objectives with you during the Service Teams’ Jour fixes so that you can add this to your planning and proposals for succeeding phases.

¹³ Furthermore, Base4NFDI will provide news items on this topic, e.g. “Base4NFDI Services and EOSC/International Interoperability” (URL: <https://base4nfdi.de/?view=article&id=144&catid=8>, last accessed: June 23, 2026). For all news items visit the [Base4NFDI News Archive](#) (last accessed: June 23, 2026).

3.3 FAIR Basic Services

An important aspect to tackle early on is the FAIRness of the services – basic services should be **FAIR-by-Design**. In the following, we present some approaches to enhance the FAIRness of a service. Consider if any of these dimensions are useful goals for your service. The most important distinction one can make is that services should either enable or enhance the FAIRness of any research data they process (if applicable) or that they or their related resources should be FAIR themselves.

3.3.1 FAIR-enabling Services

The following framework gives recommendations for service providers. These recommendations shall help them to improve their services to make them *FAIR-enabling* on a technical and a social level. A **FAIR-enabling service** would be one that increases the FAIRness of data it hosts or processes, or one that facilitates a specific FAIR principle. During the Initialisation Phase, the framework may help you to evaluate which measures could be undertaken to make your basic service FAIR-enabling and guide your future development in a way that your basic service will contribute to a FAIR research data infrastructure. Many of the aspects mentioned by this framework are good suggestions to follow for any service, not only those that try to enable FAIRness. They also touch upon aspects that are discussed in other sections of this guide (e.g. user experience, service quality, communication, legal).

[Ramezani et al. 2027] Ramezani, S. et al. (2021) 'D2.7 Framework for assessing FAIR Services'. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.6656431>.

During the FAIRsFAIR project, there were also some guidelines published on how to make a data repository align with the FAIR principles. These are useful even if the basic service you are developing is not a data repository.

[Behnke et al 2020] Behnke, C. et al. (2020) 'D2.3 Set of FAIR data repositories features'. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.5361952>.

3.3.2 FAIR Software and Software Metadata and Quality

If your basic service development includes **software development**, you are required to open up the source code of the service for reuse in a FAIR fashion. The following article provides an adaptation of the FAIR principles to research software and discusses how to increase the FAIRness of archived code.

[Barker et al 2022] Barker, M. et al. (2022) 'Introducing the FAIR Principles for research software', *Scientific Data*, 9(1), p. 622. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x> (in particular [section 2](#)).

If you want to assess the FAIRness of your software, you can use the following tool by [Spaaks et al.](#) that also generates badges for integration into source code repositories.

[Spaaks et al.] Spaaks, J. H. et al. (n/d) 'FAIR software checklist (Version 0.2.2)' [Computer software].

- Repository: <https://github.com/ardc-fair-checklist/ardc-fair-checklist.github.io> (last accessed: June 23, 2026)
- Live Demo: <https://fairsoftwarechecklist.net/v0.2/> (last accessed: June 23, 2026)

Provide your software with metadata: We recommend CodeMeta as a schema that is supported by tools to create metadata files for your source code repository.

[Jones et al. 2023] Jones, M.B. et al. (2023) 'CodeMeta: an exchange schema for software metadata. Version 3.0.' <https://w3id.org/codemeta/3.0>.

- Schema (JSON-LD): <https://w3id.org/codemeta/3.0> (last accessed: June 23, 2026).
- Homepage: <https://codemeta.github.io/index.html> (last accessed: June 23, 2026).
- Repository: <https://github.com/codemeta/codemeta> (last accessed: June 23, 2026).

[Software Heritage 2019] Software Heritage (2019): Codemeta Generator.

- Repository: <https://github.com/codemeta/codemeta-generator> (last accessed: June 23, 2026).
- Service: <https://codemeta.github.io/codemeta-generator/> (last accessed: June 23, 2026).

The following page presents five quickly implementable measures.

[DANS n.d.] Netherlands eScience Center, DANS (n.d.): Five Recommendations for FAIR Software. URL: <https://fair-software.nl/> (last accessed: June 23, 2026).

With regard to software, Base4NFDI sets expectations on software quality. You must address these when applying for the Ramp-Up Phase. They are first checked at the end of the Integration Phase and must be in place when the service is fully developed. In the

Initialisation Phase, you should already have a look at them: Apply them in the service and software evaluation task if you need to reuse existing software systems, libraries or code.

[Schäfer-Neth et al. 2025] Schäfer-Neth, C. et al. (2025) Report on Base4NFDI service integration procedures (D2.1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.17206953>, in particular the file [notes_on_software_quality.pdf](#) (download, last accessed: June 23, 2026).

4 Service Design Aspects to Consider

The following sections are not a complete methodology for service design. They introduce selected topics of particular relevance, e.g. from a legal perspective, an infrastructure perspective, or a user perspective. The structure of the guide follows these dimensions:

- [Procedural Aspects of Service Design](#)
- [User-related Aspects of Service Design](#)
- [Technological Aspects of Service Design](#)
- [Communication-related Aspects of Service Design](#)
- [Governance- and compliance-related aspects](#)

4.1 Procedural Aspects of Service Design

When designing your service, identify all **processes** that will

- constitute the **core functionality** of the basic service,
- and those that constitute and **support the delivery** of the basic service.

Document both as part of the service design to identify tasks and their dependencies, involved stakeholders, roles and responsibilities, transition and handover points, and time-related requirements. Understanding the processes that make up and support your service helps you to avoid operational inefficiencies, poor user experience, scalability issues, bottlenecks, failure points, and unexpected costs. Knowing procedural alternatives helps you find the best compromise between affordability and user experience.

Exploring the results of your user surveys and your previously defined personas and user stories¹⁴ may help uncover implicit processes or processes you were unaware of before. Explicitly document foreseeable processes that are essential to the service's user experience with documentation methods that are suited to the task and that you are familiar with (e.g. use case diagrams, service blue prints, flow charts). They help in

¹⁴ We assume that you have finished your personas and user surveys by now and have documented both in deliverable D.Ini.1 *Documentation of requirements analysis*. If not or if you are struggling with it, ask Base4NFDI for support in applying the persona method or setting up a methodically sound user survey. Cf.:

- Manske, A. et al. (2025) 'Base4NFDI – Persona Creation Kit'. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14621170>.
- Kuper, S. and Plomin, J. (2025) 'Base4NFDI – User Story Guide'. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14998462>.

reaching a common understanding about the functionality and reduce errors during development. In later stages, they help you to define test cases, perform functionality tests and observe differences in expected and actual user behaviour.

[McDermott & Sharp 2008] Sharp, A. and McDermott, P. (2009) Workflow modeling: tools for process improvement and applications development. Second edition. Boston London: Artech House. ISBN-10: 1596931922.

4.2 User-related Aspects of Service Design

The **user perspective** is paramount for the service design, in particular for defining the core-functionalities of the service in a requirements engineering process. The service support its users in their everyday tasks and in order to do so, it must be well aligned with these tasks. While the core functionality is essential for the service design, it must also encompass a wider array of user-centric considerations.

4.2.1 Accessibility

A mandatory requirement, for example, is the **accessibility** of the service to users with or without disabilities mandated by German legislation. You should consider accessibility aspects early on in your service development (“accessibility by design”) in order to be compliant with legal obligations. Base4NFDI provides a comprehensive overview over the national and EU legal framework as well as measures to meet these requirements:

[Vishen et al. 2025] Vishen, N. et al. (2025) ‘Base4NFDI– Guidelines on Application of Web Accessibility’. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15719661>.

4.2.2 User Experience and Ergonomics

Not only accessibility makes a service usable. Interactive, software-based systems should follow certain principles that make them easier to navigate and increase their **ease of use**. This saves the users time and optimises their experience. [Schäfer-Neth et al. 2025](#) give an overview over design principles for web services, user interfaces and their elements, and interactions that increase usability¹⁵. In the Initialisation Phase, you need to perform first piloting and testing activities with defined user groups (cf. [Kuper & Plomin 2025](#)). Their outcomes may feed back into your service design and prototype. Consider different usage contexts for the service like mobiles or small screens. If feasible, try to find a design that allows for a good user experience in all relevant settings/contexts.

The following ISO standard may help to gain deeper insights into the topic by introducing you to seven interaction principles and giving design recommendations for each of them.

¹⁵ See [notes_on_usability.pdf](#) (download) of [Schäfer-Neth et al. 2025](#)

[ISO 924-110:2020] ISO 9241-110:2020 Ergonomics of human-system interaction Part 110: Interaction principles. URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/75258.html> (last accessed: June 23, 2026).

[DIN EN ISO 9241-110:2020-10] DIN EN ISO 9241-110:2020-10 Ergonomie der Mensch-System-Interaktion – Teil 110: Interaktionsprinzipien (ISO 9241-110:2020). Deutsche Fassung EN ISO 9241-110:2020. URL: <https://dx.doi.org/10.31030/3147467> (last accessed: June 23, 2026).

An important success factor of any service is the overall **experience** a user has with it. This experience is a subjective impression that is formed by several dimensions, like visual design, usability, information architecture or interaction design. We do not aim to prescribe a specific tool-set to validate the user experience. Based on your personas, choose a method to validate and enhance the experience of your users that suits the kind of service you are trying to establish. For software- and information-based services this should be validated early on in the service design with UX prototypes (e.g. wireframes, mock-ups), user flows depicting user interactions for specific tasks or even early service deployments tested by first users. The service should also provide immediate and clear feedback for user actions that are understandable and offer alternatives if errors occur. Introductory works like the following help to familiarise yourself with such methods.

[ISO 9241-1:2018] ISO 9241-11:2018 Ergonomics of human-system interaction – Part 11: Usability: Definitions and concepts. URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/63500.html> (last accessed: June 23, 2026).

[DeNardis 2021] DeNardis, N. (2021) 'Introduction to User Experience Design'. URL: <https://www.tib.eu/de/suchen/id/TIBKAT:1777128242/Introduction-to-User-Experience-Design> (last accessed: June 23, 2026).

[Rosenzweig 2015] Rosenzweig, E. (2015) Successful User Experience: Strategy and Roadmaps. San Francisco: Elsevier Science & Technology. ISBN: 978-0-12-801061-7.

[Kauer-Franz & Franz 2023] Kauer-Franz, M. and Franz, B. (2023) Usability und user experience design: das umfassende Handbuch. 1. Auflage 2022, 1. korrigierter Nachdruck 2023. Bonn: Rheinwerk (Rheinwerk Computing). ISBN: 978-3-8362-8720-3.

[Hertzum 2020] Hertzum, M. (2020) Usability Testing: A Practitioner's Guide to Evaluating the User Experience. Cham: Springer International Publishing (Synthesis Lectures on Human-Centered Informatics). <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-02227-2>.

[Kuper & Plomin 2025] Kuper, S. and Plomin, J. (2025) 'Base4NFDI-Toolkit for Harmonizing Piloting and Testing Strategies'. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.17242851>.

Get in touch with a broad user basis and consider their feedback early on in order to address the more subjective aspects of the user perspective, like user experience. Address piloting and testing in your Deliverable D.Ini.5 of the Initialisation Phase.

4.2.3 Service Documentation

A crucial aspect of a user-centred perspective also concerns the **documentation** of the service. Providing documentation empowers potential users to actually use the service in a satisfactory way. It also helps you by reducing the number of support requests and the time spent explaining the functionality of your service repeatedly. Provide documentation for different user groups early on. Who may need information on what? Base4NFDI provides a comprehensive guide on documenting a service. Here, you will find suggestions on which information to include and how to provide high-quality information. Publish the documentation with an open license like [CC-BY 4.0](#).

[Manske et al. 2024] Manske, A. et al. (2024) 'Base4NFDI – Service Documentation Guide'. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.10634553>.

4.2.4 User Training

To ease the use of your basic service, provide **training** and **training materials** once the service is ready for use. Base4NFDI's Training Task Force will support you based on your service proposal and individually identified needs. [Manske 2025](#) gives a concise overview of TF Training and how it engages with you over the course of all three Base4NFDI phases.

[Manske 2025] Manske, A. (2025) 'Empowering Users – How Base4NFDI supports training development for research infrastructure services'. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.17099851>.

Related resources:

- [Manske & Petersen 2025] Manske, A. and Petersen, B. (2025) '23 TrainingThings for Writing Learning Objectives'. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15043810>.
- [Hausen et al. 2025] Hausen, D.A. et al. (2025) '23 TrainingThings For Effective Webinars'. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14792536>.
- [Petersen et al. 2025] Petersen, B. et al. (2025) 'Learning Objectives Matrix on the Topic of Research Data Management (RDM)'. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15846806>. Repository: <https://github.com/dini-ag-kim/fdm-lernziele> (last accessed: June 24, 2026).

4.3 Technological Aspects of Service Design

The basic service development's goal is usable services, i.e. services integrated into the larger research infrastructure. They shall serve multiple domains and – in the best of cases – facilitate interdisciplinary collaboration and innovation. This infrastructure is primarily located on the national level of the NFDI. Basic services, however, may also be of interest to infrastructures on a regional or international level. Emerging infrastructures (like EOSC) will play a role for the development of the NFDI (cf. [3.2 A Look Ahead – Basic Services and EOSC](#)). For this reason, it is important to strive for standardisation and **interoperability** right from the start of the service design. In the long run (i.e. after the Initialisation Phase) it is also important to make the service **reliable** and **secure**. In the Initialisation Phase, you should lay the groundwork for this.

For basic services that rely on (self-)developed software, we recommend consulting a general recommendation on software engineering published by the *Gesellschaft für Informatik e.V. (German Informatics Society)*, in particular chapter 3. The guide focuses on the development of research software in different stages of maturity. The Base4NFDI phases are aligned to the concept of the Technology-Readiness Level¹⁶, which is also employed as a reference framework of the GI-Muster-Leitlinie. It provides a good overview on methodical aspects, in particular on software architecture and design as well as software modelling. It discusses some technical basics to follow during design and development. It is a good source to consult in the future phases of your basic service development since it also addresses later stages of software engineering.

[Czerniak et al. 2025] Czerniak, A. et al. (2025) 'GI- und DE-RSE Muster-Leitlinie zur effizienten Entwicklung von Forschungssoftware'. https://doi.org/10.18420/2025-GI_DE-RSE.

4.3.1 Architecture – Components, Modules and Their Dependencies

Service design needs to address the (technical) **architecture** of the service. This comprises its structure and principles governing its organization, i.e. its **components** and their **interaction**. Outline how the service provides a specific function and how clients can **access** and utilize it. Describe the technological architecture of the service as part of your (internal) documentation, e.g. via technical architecture diagrams.

Define if and how the service can be split up into **modules**, which ones you need to develop yourself and which could be realized by existing services or components. The service's maintainability and scalability can benefit from a modular architecture and may enable parallel development and earlier testing.

¹⁶ Not all basic services developed in Base4NFDI are predominantly technical and the TRLs may not be easily applicable. Base4NFDI provides some examples on how TRLs can be interpreted for non-technical service types. You can find recommendations for TRLs 5-6 and 7-8 in chapter "TRLs (for D2.4.3)" of [Schäfer-Neth et al. 2025](#) or in section *Deliverable D.Int.2 Documentation of service maturity* in Schäfer-Neth, C., Grudskaia, A., Chen, T., Tatscheck, J., Giesler, A., Schwier, L., & Ritz, R. (2026). Requirements for Completion of the Integration Phase (1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19207558>.

Technologies used as components of your basic service should be **mature** and have an active developer community. Choose technologies that are already **compatible** with widespread solutions. It does not make sense to use the latest innovations if they do not integrate well with technologies used in the current research infrastructure.

4.3.2 Interfaces, Data Formats and Communication Protocols

A key factor for the reusability of a service is its **application programming interface (API)**. Well document the API so that users, in particular other developers, can easily oversee the structure of the data provided by the service and the offered calls and actions. It should be clear which types of endpoints are available and which parameters can be set for requests. If available, implement a standardised API for the application area of a service. For web services, the **Representational State Transfer (REST)** architectural style could be adopted using standard **HTTP methods** to perform operations on resources, which are identified by unique Uniform Resource Identifiers (URIs). If no standardised, quickly implementable API is available, start with the API design early. For its documentation, we recommend to follow the **OpenAPI specification**. If you provide several versions of the API (which would be recommended if breaking changes are introduced that affect backward compatibility), document each version. Generally, keep the documentation up to date.

If your service provides access to structured data, a **SPARQL endpoint** could be an alternative or supplement. A SPARQL endpoint allows clients to query the service's data directly using the SPARQL query language. This allows users to make very flexible requests and retrieve only the data they need with customised, to-the-point queries that are not limited to the pre-defined API routes (as with REST APIs). This is particularly useful for exposing data that follow the **Resource Description Framework (RDF)** model, as SPARQL is the standard query language for RDF. Here it is just as crucial as for REST APIs to have good documentation on the underlying data model, patterns and vocabularies that shape the knowledge graph, so that it is easier for users to utilize the endpoint. In both cases, you could consider employing tools that help explore the endpoints, like Swagger, Yasgui, visual query helpers or just valid example queries.

[OpenAPI-WhatIs?] OpenAPI Initiative (no date) What is OpenAPI? URL: <https://www.openapis.org/what-is-openapi> (last accessed: June 23, 2026).

[OpenAPI-Learn] OpenAPI Initiative (2023) OpenAPI – Getting started, and the specification explained. URL: <https://learn.openapis.org/> (last accessed: June 23, 2026).

[OpenAPI-Spec311] OpenAPI Initiative (2024) OpenAPI Specification v3.1.1. URL: <https://spec.openapis.org/oas/latest.html> (last accessed: June 23, 2026).

[OpenAPI-Examples] OpenAPI Initiative (2023) Example API Descriptions. URL: <https://learn.openapis.org/examples/> (last accessed: June 23, 2026).

[KGI4NFDI 2025] KGI4NFDI (2025) Apache Jena, QLever, Virtuoso and Wikibase Knowledge Graph Guidelines. URL: <https://kgi4nfdi.github.io/Guidelines/>

(last accessed: June 23, 2026).

The APIs should be as open as possible for easier integration to other services. Where openness is not possible, e.g. due to accessibility restrictions, implement proper authentication and authorisation mechanisms. It should be easy for legitimate users and use cases to gain access to the API. For reporting to DFG, user numbers and other KPIs are usually required. Please consider this in the API design if your service will have many programmatic requests.

Any data provided or processed by your service should be offered in well-known, **established data formats** (e.g. json, json-ld) and common **communication protocols** (https, ftp) so that they can be easily processed by the majority of users of your basic service. Since scientific data need to follow high standards with regard to trustworthiness and reproducibility, mechanisms to support data provenance tracking should be implemented where appropriate.

4.3.3 Service Performance, Health and Delivery

During service design, already think about the service **performance** and **scalability**: how can you measure these attributes and improve them when you roll the service out to communities beyond the initial test users?¹⁷ In the course of the Initialisation Phase, try to become more aware of such non-functional requirements, define and document them so that you can achieve service quality for a growing user base and new usage scenarios.

To be able to check the **service health**, plan for **monitoring** and **logging** capabilities needed to identify issues and unreliable service components: This also helps you to check up on and maintain the service's availability. You should get a feeling of how many interruptions of the service are acceptable to your users and how much time it needs to be accessible. Reduce downtimes and make the service more robust, by planning in redundancies or load balancing algorithms to handle exceptional traffic, ensure scalability or to provide failover coverage. Once the service progresses and gains users, your own development activities should not reduce the availability of the service. Set up two to three separate environments on which the service can run – at least a testing and a productive environment are required. A development environment is useful in addition, if multiple developers are involved. Use a version control tool to update your code and handle releases (e.g. with [semantic versioning](#)). Use the test environment to mature new features and roll out only well-tested features to your users. If a release still negatively affects the productive system, the tiered structure enables an easy rollback and resetting the service to a stable release. Where possible, implement automated workflows.

When the service depends on third-party service components, analyse the risks associated with such dependencies and address them in your service design. Incorporate,

¹⁷ E.g., you could measure the response times, the number of requests the service can handle per unit of time, etc. For more suggestions on key performance indicators see the supplement [notes on kpis.pdf](#) (download, last accessed: June 23, 2026) attached to [Schäfer-Neth et al. 2025](#).

for example, mitigation strategies or components that increase resilience and minimize potential disruptions. The design should already be robust enough to withstand potential failures or changes within those third-party components.

4.3.4 Testing

Providing a satisfactory service also implies **testing**. While testing and piloting (cf. [Kuper & Plomin 2025](#)) provides valuable insights for the functional service development and usability; more systematic tests are required to guarantee the overall functionality of the productive system. Consider implementing unit tests (testing of individual components in isolation) and integration tests (testing of interaction of components), automating such tests and dealing with the test results. Proper testing requires documenting and, if necessary, updating test cases and the expected behaviour of the service or its components. To perform tests, you may also require test data on which tests can be performed. With such documentation, testers will be able to evaluate whether a test was successful or failed, and to document the test results. Let tests target functionality and features, but also quality attributes of the service (e.g. performance) and system security. Changes to a productive service should only get clearance, once tests are successful, i.e. all critical remaining issues are resolved. This may require several iterations of testing and patching.

[Myers 2012] Myers, G.J. (2012) The art of software testing. 3rd ed. Hoboken, N.J: J. Wiley & Sons. ISBN: 978-1-118-13315-6.

4.3.5 Service Security

Self-developed as well as third party components must contribute to the overall information and cyber security of the service. Depending on the type of service and the data it contains or processes, there are different security requirements. Services for science should reach a very high level of trustworthiness and leave no doubt about the integrity of their data. When designing the service, try to identify potential security threats within your design and plan for countermeasures and mitigation strategies where such risks cannot be avoided. Even when prototyping, simple measures can already be implemented right from the start, e.g. enforcing strong passwords, multi-factor authentication, role-based access control following the [principle of least privilege](#), limitation of requests permitted per time frame, input validation or data encryption for data exchange.

In later phases within the Base4NFDI funding framework, you need to implement security measures that are appropriate for the required level of protection of the service and that are derived from a systematic risk analysis. Consider that the security of your service depends on your institutions' overall IT security strategies. Follow the institutions' instructions and recommendations by its IT experts. For productive operation, you should

set up continuous security monitoring to identify security incidents and to respond to them in due time. Regularly monitor and update third-party libraries and frameworks. Many vulnerabilities come from outdated components with known security flaws.

The topic of security is too broad to discuss in detail here. An internationally accepted series of standards to follow is the [ISO/IEC 27000 series](#). If you need a structured overview and entry point to the topic, use the [IT Grundschutz 2023](#) by the German Federal Office for Information Security (BSI). It gives a very good introduction to security-related topics, potential risks and requirements that must or should be met. In particular, you will find an overview of basic threats and a large number of building blocks to reduce or handle such threats. These address the technological as well as the organisational level. For software and web services we recommend the building blocks *CON.2 Data Protection*, *CON.3 Backup Concept*, *CON.8 Software Development* (in particular *CON.8.A5 Secure System Design*), *CON.10 Development of Web Applications*, *DER Detection and Reaction*, *OPS.1.1.6 Software Tests and Approvals* and *OPS.1.1.3 Patch and Change Management* and – if applicable – *OPS 2.2 Cloud Usage* and *2.3 Use of Outsourcing*. For highly developed and professionalised services that are deeply integrated into their operating institutions, you should also consider if the service requirements are well aligned to *ORP.3 Awareness and Training in Information Security*.

[\[IT Grundschutz 2023\]](#) Bundesamt für Sicherheit in der Informationstechnik (BSI) (2023) IT-Grundschutz-Kompendium. 6th edn. Köln: Reguvis. URL: <https://s.gwdg.de/202p6v> (last accessed: June 23, 2026).

- The download page for the document also links to related resources¹⁸:
 - **checklists** for all Grundschutz building blocks
 - a [matrix](#) plotting the potential threats against the building blocks
 - [mapping](#) of IT Grundschutz and related BSI standards to selected standards from the [ISO/IEC 27000 series](#)

The BSI website offers to explore security topics from different perspectives, e.g. [recommendations based on security targets](#), [recommendations based on threats](#), or from the perspective of specific topics like [AI](#), [cryptography](#), or [others](#).

Include plans for the restoration and continued operation of your service after undesired events into your design: you can implement them in later stages of development. Focus on high-probability risks first, i.e. events that may likely occur and affect the availability of the service during “days as usual” without any major catastrophes or crises happening.

¹⁸ If no link is provided look for “Weiterführende Informationen (Edition 2023)”.

4.4 Communication-related Aspects of Service Design

4.4.1 Service Website and Communication Channels

Your service design should also include communication-related aspects. Base4NFDI creates a project page for your service on the Base4NFDI website¹⁹, providing contact information, service description, info about project team, current funding phase and outputs as well as an overview over events related to your service²⁰. In addition, set up a separate service homepage. Base4NFDI provides a [Mkdocs](#) and a [Hugo](#) template for a GitHub- or self-hosted page to promote your service. Base4NFDI can provide a domain for it.

[Ritter et al. 2024] Ritter, X. et al. (2024) 'Base4NFDI Website Policy'. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14245434>.

Users of your service should know how to contact you, get support and receive information about the service. Establish channels to reach out to your users, e.g. in case of updates or errors or anything else they need to know. Define **communication and support channels** that you deem appropriate. We recommend setting up a mailing list but it may also be feasible to have a channel on the NFDI Rocket Chat to get in touch with your NFDI user base quickly. To reach users beyond the NFDI it would be feasible to set up social media accounts where users, who are not currently part of an NFDI consortium, a section, or a directly affiliated institution, may discover your service. You are also free to choose other, more elaborate pathways (e.g. a helpdesk) – in any case, you should actively monitor any channels you establish and be responsive to them.

4.4.2 Change Management and Communication

An important part of your user-related communication concerns the **announcement and management of changes** – draft a strategy on how this will be handled for the basic service. Even in an early prototype stage, we recommend to notify users if changes are made to the live service (especially if these involve service downtimes). Try to anticipate possible consequences those changes may have on your users. If you are not able to do so (which is completely understandable), make users aware of planned changes in advance so that they have the opportunity to respond, adapt their own plans and estimate the time required to adjust. Wherever possible, try to **enable backwards-compatibility**. If this is not possible, provide comprehensible information about breaking changes.

¹⁹ URL: <https://base4nfdi.de/projects> (last accessed: June 23, 2026)

²⁰ See for example the Base4NFDI project page for PID4NFDI: <https://base4nfdi.de/projects/pid4nfdi> (last accessed: June 23, 2026)

4.5 Governance- and Compliance-related Aspects of Service Design

In chapter [4.1 Procedural Aspects of Service Design](#), we already discussed workflow aspects – those relating to user-interactions and those relating to service operation. The latter are closely related to the governance of the service and its development.

4.5.1 Assigning Tasks and Responsibilities

Sketch ownership, roles and responsibilities in the design and fill them by actual people in the development process – in particular when the service reaches a productive state. This enables you to enforce policies for the service development and have clear responsibilities for decisions concerning the service and any changes to it. A [responsibility assignment matrix](#) (RACI matrix) is a good tool to document these responsibilities for the service’s developmental and operational phase. It splits an operation or project into several tasks and distinguishes roles to be involved for different reasons.

Role Task	Role 1 (e.g. software developer)	Role 2 (e.g. product owner)
Task 1	R (esponsible) = person is assigned to the task and responsible for its completion	A (ccountable) = person has ownership over the task and makes the final decision
Task 2	C (onsulted) = person must be consulted before a decision is made	I (nformed) = person must be informed that a decision has been taken

Again, not all responsibilities need to be final in the service design draft or even by the end of the Initialisation Phase –update and refine them as the service matures. In the beginning, the focus may be more about development; at the end of the service development, it must also touch upon issues of sustainability like long-term funding, community governance, maintenance etc. In the early stages, it can guide the processes set up by you as a team.

4.5.2 Compliance

Compliance with regulatory, legal, organisational, and ethical requirements is a quality attribute of your service. In particular, we would like to bring your attention to 1) issues of licensing/ license compatibility, 2) the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and 3) accessibility. The first two will be discussed in the following, while [4.2 User-related Aspects of Service Design](#) already addressed accessibility.

4.5.2.1 Licenses and License Compatibility

When re-using different materials or software for your service, make sure that their licenses are open, permissive, and compatible (cf. [Czerniak et al. 2025](#)). The Licensing Assistant by the European Commission and its [Compatibility Checker](#) are useful tools to

check if the licenses of components are compatible. If you want a more programmatic approach to ensure license compatibility of software from different sources, we recommend REUSE.

[FSFE 2025] Free Software Foundation Europe e.V. (2025) REUSE Software. URL: <https://reuse.software/> (last accessed: June 23, 2026).

- API: <https://api.reuse.software/>

[Haerter 2025] Haerter, A. (2025) 'FSFE REUSE: Einfache Lizenz- und Quellenverwaltung für Software-Projekte. Vortrag bei der Gulaschprogrammierenacht 23'. URL: <https://media.ccc.de/v/gpn23-268-fsfe-reuse-einfache-lizenz-und-quellenverwaltung-fr-software-projekte> (last accessed: June 23, 2026).

[Haerter 2025b] Haerter, A. (2025) 'Making sense of software licensing with FSFE REUSE: A beginner's guide for open source developers. Post at fedora Magazine'. URL: <https://fedoramagazine.org/beginners-guide-for-open-source-developers-f-or-software-licensing-with-fsfe-reuse/> (last accessed: June 23, 2026).

4.5.2.2 Personal Data and Protection

In the Initialisation phase, Base4NFDI will ask you to set up a website where users can learn more about your project and the service you are trying to establish. The website must be compliant to GDPR if visitors can use it to contact you, and thereby provide **personal data**. [Ritter et al. 2024](#) provide guidance on setting up the page and on designing a **privacy policy**.

Identifying all GDPR-related facts to be processed by your service is a unique undertaking – we recommend getting in touch with your **data protection officer** (DPO) when drafting the service design. They help identify all relevant aspects and can provide you with templates for a **data protection concept** and a **data protection policy** for your web service. It makes sense to start the data protection concept early to have sufficient time for clarifications with the DPO at your institution. The service design documentation should also elaborate how personal data – if any – can be protected by technical and organisational measures (TOMs), and how requests for the deletion of personal data will be handled. Implement data protection by design and default.

5 Conclusion: Don't Panic!

Service design is the process that creates, maintains and improves the value of a service for both service users and providers – accordingly, lots of groundwork for your service is covered by this very task.

This guide's intention is to help you navigate the jungle of service design aspects to consider. It is supposed to enable you to organise all processes, technologies and

interactions that are essential for the delivery of your service. It shall prevent you from missing any important aspects.

Remember: Service design should be performed throughout the entire lifecycle of a service – the design grows iteratively. Do not be too perfectionistic and do not forget: In the Initialisation Phase, you are supposed to make a service design *draft* that guides you and can be improved and detailed later. Use this guide to pick the most relevant dimensions for the type of service you are trying to establish and if you do not feel comfortable with any of the dimensions sketched here, see this as an opportunity to address them in your work plans in your Integration or Ramp-up Phase proposals.

Image Credits

Puzzle icon by [Yudhi Restu](#) on [Flaticon](#)

User interface icon by [Iconjam](#) on [Flaticon](#)

Best seller icon by [Hazicon](#) on [Flaticon](#)

Cogs icon by [Prosymbols Premium](#) on [Flaticon](#)

Usability icon by [Bharat Icons](#) on [Flaticon](#)

Agreement icon by [Uniconlabs](#) on [Flaticon](#)